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Two new protected areas to conserve saigas in Kazakhstan

The Bokeyorda State Nature Reserve and the Ashiozek State Wildlife Sanctuary (Zakaznik), both with federal status, have been established in the western part of West Kazakhstan province, in Kaztal, Zhanybek, Bokey Orda and Zhanakala Districts. Both protected areas were designated following a decree by the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan issued on 25th May, 2022, and officially opened on 1st July 2022. The Bokeyorda Reserve consists of two sections, Aralsor and Zhanakala, and has a total area of 343,040.1 hectares. The Ashiozek Zakaznik is 314,504.1 ha in area and adjoins the Aralsor section of the Bokeyorda reserve.

The main goals of both reserves is to protect saigas and conserve the most characteristic landscapes and ecosystems of the northern part of the Caspian Lowland. The Aralsor section and Ashiozek Zakaznik almost entirely cover the drainless basin of the seasonal Ashiozek River with all its main tributaries and the system of salt pans at its mouth. The Zhanakala section includes a significant part of the system of floodplains and salt pans formed by the Kamysh-Samar Lakes, fed by the Big and Small Uzen Rivers, as well as the adjacent periphery of the Naryn sands.

Vegetation cover includes various typical and psammophytic, mainly salty, desert steppe plant communities, dominated by xerophytic bunchgrasses and forbs (specifically *Artemisia* spp., *Tanacetum achilleifolium*, etc.) combined with northern desert communities dominated by dwarf shrubs of *Artemisia* spp., *Atriplex cana*, and *Anabasis salsa*, saline meadows and inland salt marshes, hyperhalophytic saltwort deserts around numerous salt flats, and psammophytic deserts

dominated mainly by *Artemisia arenaria* and *Agropyron desertorum*. Trees are scarce; small groves and open woodlands of oleaster and tamarix are scattered along salty gullies and the edges of salt flat depressions, with single trees and small stands of black poplars and white willows in valleys. Low shrubs, specifically *Spiraea hypericifolia* and *Rhamnus cathartica*, form thickets in gullies and terraces of river valleys and salt lake depressions.

Saigas inhabit almost all parts of the new reserves. The Aralsor section and Ashiozek Zakaznik include important calving sites and areas where the animals concentrate in summer and autumn, and are crossed by the seasonal migration routes of the western group of the Ural saiga population. The Zhanakala section encompasses wintering sites used by a part of this group, and formerly included the wintering and calving grounds used by the eastern group of this population. According to ACBK specialists, in recent years, there are 100,000 or more saigas in the Aralsor section and Ashiozek Zakaznik. In the Zhanakala

Ashchyozek river in the Bokeyorda reserve. Photo by Ilya Smelansky/ASBK

section, saiga numbers are currently relatively small but may grow to tens or even hundreds of thousands of individuals if the Kamysh-Samar floodplains are flooded.

The Bokeyorda State Nature Reserve is in a specific category of protected area; a nature conservation and research institution with exclusive land use rights for the entire territory, part of which is strictly protected. One of the essential characteristics of this type of protected area is that it is divided into zones. In addition to the strictly protected core, the reserve has a buffer zone where some activities are allowed, such as traditional land use (in this case, moderate grazing and haymaking), research, tourism and some other activities compatible with the environmental objectives of the protected area. In addition to the buffer zone inside the reserve, it is surrounded by a 2–3 km-wide protected transition zone all along the perimeter.

In contrast to the reserve, there are about 200 leased farming plots within the zakaznik. These are all livestock breeding farms using the natural ecosystems of the zakaznik for grazing and hayfields. The use of natural resources will be limited and regulated within the zakaznik. The zakaznik

Map of Bokeyorda State Nature Reserve and the Ashiozek State Wildlife Sanctuary

does not have its own administration and will be managed and protected by the directorate of the Bokeyorda Reserve.

Documents justifying the creation of both protected areas were prepared in 2012–2013, as part of the project “Conservation and Sustainable Management of Steppe Ecosystems” implemented by the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan/GEF/UNDP.

By the time these justifications had been developed, the Ural saiga population had not yet recovered after a catastrophic decline at the turn of the 21st century, having only reached 20,000-30,000 individuals. Now it is 40 times larger, with 800,000 saigas recorded in spring 2022. Livestock numbers have also increased significantly in the 4 districts where the reserve and the zakaznik are located, with cattle growing 2-fold, sheep 1.5x and horses 2.5x. All this creates new challenges for the protected areas Administrators and for environmental organisations, setting new tasks that were not envisaged in the original documents.

ACBK, working in partnership with the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB), is assisting the Forestry and Wildlife Committee under the Ministry of Ecology, Geology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Kazakhstan in planning activities within the new reserve and zakaznik. These include developing a 5-year management plan, a biodiversity monitoring programme, training courses for the staff, and providing vehicles and field and research equipment.

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